

(1 g.) and ethyl α -bromoisobutyrate, separated from dilute alcohol in needles which melted at 140° (mixed m.p. 140°).

THE MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
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Received December 10, 1934.

Halogenation. Part X. Preparation of Mixed Halogen Derivatives of Xylenes.

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The study of the literature shows that the chloro-iodo and bromo-iodo compounds of xylenes have not been obtained before. The majority of the mixed halogen derivatives of the aromatic hydrocarbons have usually been prepared by indirect methods from the diamino-compounds by successively replacing the amino groups by the halogen atoms by the Sandmeyer's reaction. Chlorotoluenes have been successfully iodinated in this laboratory in presence of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid or mixture of nitro-sulphonic and fuming nitric acids. (Varma and Sahay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 293).

It has been possible to iodinate the chloro- and bromoxylenes in presence of nitrosulphonic acid mixture and very good yields of the chloro-iodo and bromo-iodo compounds have been obtained. 2-Chloro-*p*-xylene and 4-chloro-*m*-xylene on iodination give two new chloro-iodo derivatives, which from analogy with the corresponding chloro and bromo derivatives seem to be 2-chloro-5-iodo-*p*-xylene and 4-chloro-6-iodo-*m*-xylene respectively. 4-Bromo-*o*-xylene on iodination and 4-iodo-*o*-xylene on bromination gave the same bromo-iodo derivatives of *o*-xylene. Hence the compound must be 4-bromo-5-iodo-*o*-xylene. In case of *m*-xylene, 4-bromo-*m*-xylene and 4-iodo-*m*-xylene, the former by iodination and the latter by bromination gave the same bromo-iodo-derivative. The compound in question is, therefore, 4-bromo-6-iodo-*m*-xylene. In the same way 2-bromo-*p*-xylene and 2-iodo-*p*-xylene gave the same bromo-iodo-*p*-xylenes. The last compound seems to be 2-bromo-5-iodo-*p*-xylene from analogy with other halogen compounds of *p*-xylene.

6-Chloro 4-bromo-*m*-xylene has been prepared before (Noyes, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1898, 20, 798) from 6-bromo-4-amino-*m*-xylene. 2-Chloro-5-bromo-*m*-xylene has been obtained (Willgerodt and Wolfien, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1889, ii, 39, 403) by the action of bromine on 2-chloro *p*-xylene. These compounds have been prepared by us in good yields by direct bromination in presence of nitro-sulphonic acid mixture and other substances.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Chloro-5-iodo-p-xylene.—To 2-chloro-*p*-xylene (5 c. c.), powdered iodine (5 g.), acetic acid (5 c. c.) and carbon tetrachloride (5 c. c.) in a flask with a reflux condenser, heated on a sand-bath the temperature of which was raised to about 135°, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (4 c.c.) was added (1 c. c. at a time) in about 2 minutes. After the addition of the acid mixture the temperature of the sand-bath was raised to about 250° and maintained at that temperature for about 45 minutes. The reaction product was cooled, extracted with carbon tetrachloride, the extract being washed with a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide till free from iodine and then with distilled water, dried over fused calcium chloride and allowed to stand on a watch glass overnight, when crystals separated out. These were recrystallised from ether, m.p. 46°. (Found: total halogen, 60.05. C_8H_8ClI requires total halogen 60.98 per cent). It is easily soluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ether, benzene and xylenes. It is slightly soluble in methyl alcohol, cold acetic acid and more on warming, yield 7 g.

4-Chloro-6-iodo-m-xylene.—To 4-chloro-*m*-xylene (5 c. c.), powdered iodine (5 g.), acetic acid (5 c. c.) and carbon tetrachloride (5 c. c.) in a flask and heated on a sand-bath to about 145°, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (4.5 c. c.) was added and then worked up as described before. The solid product (5.5 g.) was crystallised from warm acetic acid, m. p. 44°. (Found: total halogen, 60.15. C_8H_8ClI requires total halogen, 60.98 per cent).

4-Bromo-5-iodo-o-xylene (i) From 4-bromo-o-xylene.—To 4-bromo-*o*-xylene (5 c. c.), powdered iodine (4.5 g.), acetic acid (5 c.c.) and carbon tetrachloride (4 c.c.) in a flask and heated on a sand-bath, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (3 c.c.) was added drop by drop in about 15 minutes and the heating continued for about 2 hours more. The product was washed free of iodine by a dilute solution of caustic soda, dried over fused calcium chloride and left to stand overnight on a

watch glass when the temperature of the room was about 15°. Needle-shaped crystals separated out. Further crop of crystals was obtained from the mother liquor by cooling it in a freezing mixture, m. p. 68·5°, yield 4·2 g. (Found: total halogen, 66·03. C_8H_8BrI requires total halogen, 66·56 per cent). The solubility of the compound is the same as that of chloro-iodo derivatives.

(ii) *From 4-iodo-o-xylene.*—To 4-iodo-o-xylene (5 c.c.) and iodine (0·2 g.) in a flask with a reflux condenser, bromine (1·8 c.c.) was added drop by drop in about 10 minutes and the reaction product heated on a water-bath for about an hour more. The product was worked up as described above and the crystals isolated by cooling in a freezing mixture, m. p. 68·5°, yield 6 g. It is found to be identical with the compound obtained by iodinating 4-bromo-o-xylene. If bromination is conducted at the room temperature with aluminium chloride as a carrier the yield is 4·5 g.

4-Bromo-6-iodo-m-xylene (i) *From 4-bromo-m-xylene.*—To 4-bromo-m-xylene (5 c.c.), powdered iodine (5·5 g.), acetic acid (5 c.c.) and carbon tetrachloride (5 c.c.) in a flask, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (3 c.c.) was added drop by drop and heated for an hour more. The reaction product was worked up as described above. Needle shaped crystals (3·2 g.) were obtained, m. p. 47°. (Found: total halogen, 66·0. C_8H_8BrI requires total halogen, 66·56 per cent).

(ii) *From 4-iodo-m-xylene.*—To 4-iodo-m-xylene (3 c.c.) and iodine (0·1 g.) in a flask, bromine (2 c.c.) was added and the mixture heated on a water-bath for about 2 hours. The product was worked up as described above, yield 2·2 g. and with thalious chloride, 2·2 g.

2-Bromo-5-iodo p-xylene (i) *From 2-bromo-p-xylene.*—To 2-bromo-p-xylene (5 c.c.), iodine (4·5 g.), acetic acid (5 c.c.) and carbon tetrachloride (5 c.c.) in a flask and heated on a sand-bath to about 150°, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (4 c.c.) was added (1 c.c. at a time) in about 15 minutes and then the temperature of the bath maintained at 230°-240° for about 45 minutes. The bromo-iodo compound was isolated by means of a freezing mixture as in the preceding cases. After crystallising from chloroform, the compound melted at 73°, yield 7·0 g. (Found: total halogen, 66·14. C_8H_8BrI requires, total halogen, 66·56 per cent).

(ii) *From 2-iodo-p-xylene.*—To 2-iodo-p-xylene (5 c.c.) and iodine (0·2 g.), bromine (1·8 c.c.) was added drop by drop in about 10 minutes and heated on a water-bath for about an hour. The bromo-iodo compound was isolated as before, yield 7·5 g. When the experiment

was conducted at the ordinary temperature without any halogen carrier, the yield was 4.3 g.

4-Chloro-6-bromo-m-xylene.—To 4-chloro-*m*-xylene (2 c. c.) and bromine (1 c.c.) in a flask and heated on a water bath, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (1 c.c.) was added drop by drop and the heating continued for half an hour more. The product was worked up as described above. The crystals from ether melted at 68° and were identified to be 4-chloro-6-bromo-*m*-xylene, yield 3 g. In presence of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid the yield was 2.8 g. and in presence of iodine as carrier 2.6 g.

2-Chloro-5-bromo-p-xylene.—To 2-chloro-*p*-xylene (3 c.c.) and bromine (1 c. c.) in a flask, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (1 c.c.) was added drop by drop and heated on a water bath for about 45 minutes. The chloro-bromo compound was obtained as described above and the crystals separated by cooling in a freezing mixture, m. p. 66°, yield 3.1 g. With strong nitric acid the yield was 2.8 g.

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Received January 4, 1935,

Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part II. The Structure of the Triphenylmethane Dyes.

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The constitution of the triphenylmethane dyes has been the subject of much controversy, the problem being not yet settled. The mother substances of the group, triphenylmethane and triphenyl carbinol are colourless. The *leuco*-bases as well as the dye-bases (when freshly prepared) are also colourless, while the salts are intensely coloured substances. It thus appears that there must be some fundamental difference in structure between the colourless and the coloured compounds. The colourless compounds are represented by benzenoid configuration while various formulæ have been proposed